

Analytical formulation of a 2+2+1 bolt-row activation model for extended end-plate connections

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document presents an analytical calculation procedure for extended end-plate beam-to-beam connections, developed within the framework of the component method defined in Eurocode 3. The formulation is specifically intended for inclined connections in which the stress distribution within the end-plate differs from the assumptions adopted in conventional orthogonal configurations.

The proposed procedure extends the standard analytical approach by explicitly incorporating the intermediate erection bolt-row as an active component in the evaluation of the bending resistance of the joint. While the Eurocode formulation typically neglects this row in simplified calculations, numerical analyses have shown that, in inclined connections, stress redistribution within the end-plate may lead to its participation in tension under both sagging and hogging bending moments.

The formulation presented here preserves the theoretical basis and calculation principles of Eurocode 3, including the representation of bolt-rows through equivalent T-stub mechanisms and the sequential evaluation of tensile resistance. The proposed extension consists of modifying the bolt-row activation pattern to account for a distributed resisting mechanism, here referred to as a 2+2+1 bolt-row configuration, in which the intermediate row contributes to the overall bending capacity of the connection.

This document provides the complete set of analytical expressions and calculation steps required to implement this extended formulation. The procedure is intended to facilitate the practical evaluation of inclined end-plate connections and to support the interpretation of stress redistribution effects observed in numerical simulations.

The formulation may be applied to a wide range of geometrical configurations, although its use should be considered in conjunction with the limitations discussed in the associated research work.

The novelty of this formulation lies in the reinterpretation of bolt-row activation as a distributed resisting mechanism rather than a discrete one.

2. GEOMETRICAL DEFINITION AND NOTATION

The geometric parameters and notation adopted in this formulation are consistent with those defined in Eurocode 3 for extended end-plate connections.

Figure 1 shows the geometric parameters defining the configuration of the joint with 2+2+1 bolt-rows. The erection bolt row has been considered in the calculation process as an active row, unlike its treatment in Eurocode 3; it has therefore been designated as the second inner bolt-row in the development of the calculations

Fig. 1. Definition of bolt spacing and edge distance parameters in 2+2+1 resisting pattern.

2.1. LIST OF SYMBOLS

a_f	Effective throat thickness of flange-to-plate welds	p_2	Spacing between adjacent bolt-rows
a_f	Effective throat thickness of web-to-plate welds	t_{ep}	Thickness of the end-plate
$b_{eff,t,wb}$	Effective width of the beam web in tension	t_{fb}	Flange thickness of the connected beam
b_{ep}	Width of the end-plate	t_{wb}	Web thickness of the connected beam
d	Bolt diameter	w	Spacing between adjacent bolt-rows
d_0	Diameter of the bolt hole	z_1	Throat thickness of the upper flange-to-end-plate weld in tension
d_1	Distance from the upper edge of the beam flange to the edge of the end-plate	z_2	Throat thickness of the lower flange-to-end-plate weld in tension
d_2	Spacing between first and second bolt-row	A_s	Tensile stress area of the bolt
d_i	Lever arm between the centroid of bolt-row i and the center of compression	$F_{c,fb,Rd}$	Compression resistance of the connected flange and web
d_m	Mean of the across points and across flat dimensions of the bolted head or the nut, whichever is smaller	$F_{p,Rd}$	Punching resistance of the bolt head or nut
$e_{1,lf}$	Bolt-to-edge distance in the direction of the load transfer (lower flange of beam)	$F_{t,Rd}$	Design tension resistance per bolt
$e_{1,uf}$	Bolt-to-edge distance in the direction of the load transfer (upper flange of beam)	$F_{t1,Rd}$	Design tension resistance of outer bolt-row (first bolt-row)
e_2	Bolt-to-edge distance measured perpendicular to the main load direction	$F_{t2,Rd}$	Design tension resistance of first inner bolt-row (second bolt-row)
f_u	Ultimate strength	$F_{t3,Rd}$	Design tension resistance of second inner bolt-row (third bolt-row)
f_{ub}	Ultimate tensile strength for bolts	$F_{ti,ep,Rd}$	Design tension resistance of a T-stub flange in bolt-row i
f_y	Yield strength	$F_{t2+3,ep,Rd}$	Design tension resistance of a T-stub flange in group of first and second inner bolt-rows
h_b	Depth of the connected beam	$F_{ti,wb,Rd}$	Design tension resistance of the beam web for bolt-row i

h_{ep}	Depth of the end-plate	$F_{t2+3,wb,Rd}$	Design tension resistance of the beam web for group of first and second inner bolt-rows
$l_{eff,icp}$	Effective T-stub length for circular bolt pattern (bolt- row i)	$F_{T1,Rd}$	Design tension resistance of a T-stub flange for failure Mode 1
$l_{eff,inc}$	Effective T-stub length for non-circular bolt pattern (bolt- row i)	$F_{T2,Rd}$	Design tension resistance of a T-stub flange for failure Mode 2
m	Distance from the bolt-row axis to the web plastic hinge	$F_{T3,Rd}$	Design tension resistance of a T-stub flange for failure Mode 3
$p_{1.1.lf}$	Spacing between the first and second bolt-rows (lower flange)	$M_{c,Rd}$	Design moment resistance of the beam cross-section
$p_{1.1.uf}$	Spacing between the first and second bolt-rows (upper flange)	$M_{j,Rd-}$	Design moment resistance of the joint for clockwise bending moment
$p_{1.1.1lf}$	Spacing between the bolt-row located outside the lower flange and the flange axis	$M_{j,Rd+}$	Design moment resistance of the joint for anticlockwise bending moment
$p_{1.1.1uf}$	Spacing between the bolt-row located outside the upper flange and the flange axis	$M_{pl1,Rd}$	Plastic resistance moment of the equivalent T-stub for Mode 1
$p_{1.1.2lf}$	Spacing between the first inner bolt-row and the lower flange axis	$M_{pl2,Rd}$	Plastic resistance moment of the equivalent T-stub for Mode 2
$p_{1.1.2uf}$	Spacing between the first inner bolt-row and the upper flange axis	$W_{e,lyb}$	Elastic section modulus
$p_{1.2.lf}$	Spacing between the second and third bolt-rows (lower flange)	α, β	Angles of the joint
$p_{1.2.uf}$	Spacing between the second and third bolt-rows (upper flange)	α	Effective length factor for bolts located at plate corners
$p_{1.3}$	Spacing between innermost bolt-rows	γ_{M0}, γ_{M2}	Partial safety factors

3. MECHANICAL INTERPRETATION OF THE 2+2+1 MODEL

The conventional component method assumes that only the bolt-rows located within the tension zone contribute to the bending resistance of the joint. This assumption is based on the existence of a well-defined neutral axis and a localized deformation mechanism.

However, numerical results obtained for inclined beam-to-beam end-plate connections indicate that this assumption is no longer strictly valid. The inclination between connected members produces a shift of the neutral axis within the end-plate and promotes a redistribution of stresses that extends beyond the classical tension zone.

As a result, bolt-rows that would not be considered active according to the standard formulation may develop non-negligible tensile forces. This effect is particularly relevant for the intermediate bolt-row, which is traditionally regarded as an erection or constructional element.

From a mechanical standpoint, the behaviour of the joint can therefore be reinterpreted as a distributed resisting mechanism. Instead of a discrete set of active rows, the connection develops a continuous redistribution of tensile forces among the available bolt-rows.

This leads to a 2+2+1 resisting pattern, in which the outer and first inner bolt-rows primarily resist bending in each direction, and the intermediate row contributes to both bending directions through stress redistribution.

This interpretation provides the basis for extending the analytical formulation of the component method.

4. ANALYTICAL ASSUMPTIONS AND EXTENSION OF THE COMPONENT METHOD

The proposed formulation preserves the fundamental principles of the Eurocode 3 component method. In particular, the representation of bolt-rows through equivalent T-stub mechanisms and the evaluation of failure modes remain unchanged.

The extension introduced in this work affects only the bolt-row activation scheme. Instead of assuming a fixed set of active rows based on a predefined neutral axis, the formulation considers that all bolt-rows may potentially contribute to the tensile resistance of the joint.

The intermediate bolt-row is therefore explicitly included in the calculation process and treated as an active component. In addition, the interaction between adjacent bolt-rows is evaluated through group mechanisms, allowing the redistribution of forces to be captured within the analytical framework.

This approach enables the analytical model to reflect the distributed resisting behaviour observed in numerical simulations, while maintaining full compatibility with the Eurocode formulation.

5. ANALYTICAL FORMULATION

5.1. Bolt tension resistance $F_{t,Rd}$

$F_{t,Rd} = \frac{0.9f_{ub}A_s}{\gamma_{M2}}$	$F_{p,Rd} = \frac{0.6\pi d_m t_p f_u}{\gamma_{M2}}$
$F_{t,Rd} = \min(F_{t,Rd}; F_{p,Rd})$	

5.2. Calculation of the joint for hogging bending moment $M_{j,Rd}$

5.2.1. Outer bolt-row (1st bolt-row)

$e_x = e_{1,uf}$	$m_x = d_1 - e_x - 0.8z_1$
$d_1 = e_1 + p_{1.1.1} - \frac{t_{fb}/\cos\alpha}{2}$	$z_1 = \frac{a_f}{\cos\left(\frac{90 + \alpha}{2}\right)}$
$n = \min(e_{min}; 1.25m_x)$	

Calculation of effective lengths

• Circular patterns	• Non-circular patterns
$l_{eff,1,cp} = \min\left(\frac{2\pi m_x}{\pi m_x + w}; \pi m_x + 2e\right)$	$l_{eff,1,nc} = \min\left(\frac{4m_x + 1.25e_x}{e + 2m_x + 0.625e_x}; \frac{0.5b_{ep}}{0.5w + 2m_x + 0.625e_x}\right)$

Design tension resistance $F_{t1,ep,Rd}$

• Failure mode 1	$l_{eff,1} = \min(l_{eff,1,cp}; l_{eff,1,nc})$ $M_{pl,1,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,1} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$ $F_{T1,Rd} = \frac{4M_{pl,1,Rd}}{m_x}$
• Failure mode 2	$l_{eff,2} = l_{eff,1,nc}$ $M_{pl,2,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,2} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$ $F_{T2,Rd} = \frac{2M_{pl,2,Rd} + n \sum F_{t,Rd}}{m_x + n}$
• Failure mode 3	$F_{T3,Rd} = \sum F_{t,Rd}$

Resistance of outer bolt-row $F_{t1,Rd}$

$F_{t1,Rd} = F_{t1,ep,Rd} = \min(F_{T1,Rd}; F_{T2,Rd}; F_{T3,Rd})$
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5.2.2. First inner bolt-row (2nd bolt-row)

$e_x = e_{1,uf}$	$m_2 = e_x + d_2 - d_1 - \frac{t_{fb}}{\cos\alpha} - 0.8z_2$
$z_2 = \frac{a_f}{\cos\left(\frac{90-\alpha}{2}\right)}$	$m = \frac{w - t_{wb} - 2 \cdot 0.8 \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot a_w}{2}$
	$n = \min(e_{min}; 1.25m)$

Calculation of effective lengths

• Circular patterns	• Non-circular patterns
$l_{eff,2,cp} = 2\pi m$	$l_{eff,2,nc} = \alpha m$

Design tension resistance $F_{t2,ep,Rd}$

• Failure mode 1	$l_{eff,1} = \min(l_{eff,2,cp}; l_{eff,2,nc})$ $M_{pl,1,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,1} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$ $F_{T1,Rd} = \frac{4M_{pl,1,Rd}}{m}$
• Failure mode 2	$l_{eff,2} = l_{eff,2,nc}$ $M_{pl,2,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,2} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$ $F_{T2,Rd} = \frac{2M_{pl,2,Rd} + n \sum F_{t,Rd}}{m + n}$
• Failure mode 3	$F_{T3,Rd} = \sum F_{t,Rd}$
$F_{t2,ep,Rd} = \min(F_{T1,Rd}; F_{T2,Rd}; F_{T3,Rd})$	

Design tension resistance of the beam web $F_{t2,wb,Rd}$

$b_{eff,t,wb} = \min(l_{eff,2,cp}; l_{eff,2,nc})$
$F_{t2,wb,Rd} = \frac{b_{eff,t,wb} t_{wb} f_{y,wb}}{\gamma_{M0}}$

Design compression resistance of a beam flange and the beam web $F_{c,fb,Rd}$

$M_{c,Rd} = W_{el,yb} f_{yb} / \gamma_{M0}$
$F_{c,fb,Rd} = \frac{M_{c,Rd}}{(h_b - t_{fb})}$

Resistance of first inner bolt-row $F_{t2,Rd}$

$F_{t2,Rd} = \min\left(\begin{array}{l} F_{t2,ep,Rd} = \min(F_{T1,Rd}; F_{T2,Rd}; F_{T3,Rd}); \\ F_{t2,wb,Rd}; \\ F_{c,fb,Rd} - F_{t1,Rd} \end{array}\right)$

5.2.3. Second inner bolt-row (erection bolt-row or 3rd bolt-row)

Calculation of effective lengths

• Circular patterns	• Non-circular patterns
$l_{eff,3,cp} = 2\pi m$	$l_{eff,3,nc} = 4m + 1.25e$

Design tension resistance $F_{t3,ep,Rd}$

• Failure mode 1	$l_{eff,1} = \min(l_{eff,3,cp}; l_{eff,3,nc})$ $M_{pl,1,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,1} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$
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	$F_{T1,Rd} = \frac{4M_{pl,1,Rd}}{m}$
• Failure mode 2	$l_{eff,2} = l_{eff,3,nc}$ $M_{pl,2,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,2} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$ $F_{T2,Rd} = \frac{2M_{pl,2,Rd} + n \sum F_{t,Rd}}{m+n}$
• Failure mode 3	$F_{T3,Rd} = \sum F_{t,Rd}$
$F_{t3,ep,Rd} = \min(F_{T1,Rd}; F_{T2,Rd}; F_{T3,Rd})$	

Design tension resistance of the beam web $F_{t3,wb,Rd}$

$b_{eff,t,wb} = \min(l_{eff,3,cp}; l_{eff,3,nc})$
$F_{t3,wb,Rd} = \frac{b_{eff,t,wb} t_{wb} f_{y,wb}}{\gamma_{M0}}$

Design compression resistance of a beam flange and the beam web $F_{c,fb,Rd}$

$M_{c,Rd} = W_{el,yb} f_{yb} / \gamma_{M0}$
$F_{c,fb,Rd} = \frac{M_{c,Rd}}{(h_b - t_{fb})}$

Group of first and second inner bolt-rows (2nd and 3rd bolt-rows)

Calculation of effective lengths

• First inner bolt-row considered as part of a group	
Circular patterns	Non-circular patterns
$l_{eff,2,cp} = \pi m + p$	$l_{eff,2,nc} = 0.5p + am - (2m + 0.625e)$
• Second inner bolt-row considered as part of a group	
Circular patterns	Non-circular patterns
$l_{eff,3,cp} = \pi m + p$	$l_{eff,3,nc} = 2m + 0.625e + 0.5p$
• First and second inner bolt-row	
Circular patterns	Non-circular patterns
$l_{eff,2+3,cp} = l_{eff,2,cp} + l_{eff,3,cp}$	$l_{eff,2+3,nc} = l_{eff,2,nc} + l_{eff,3,nc}$

Design tension resistance $F_{t2+3,ep,Rd}$

• Failure mode 1	$l_{eff,1} = \min(l_{eff,2+3,cp}; l_{eff,2+3,nc})$ $M_{pl,1,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,1} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$ $F_{T1,Rd} = \frac{4M_{pl,1,Rd}}{m}$
• Failure mode 2	$l_{eff,2} = l_{eff,2+3,nc}$ $M_{pl,2,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,2} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$ $F_{T2,Rd} = \frac{2M_{pl,2,Rd} + n \sum F_{t,Rd}}{m+n}$
• Failure mode 3	$F_{T3,Rd} = \sum F_{t,Rd}$
$F_{t2+3,ep,Rd} = \min(F_{T1,Rd}; F_{T2,Rd}; F_{T3,Rd})$	

Design tension resistance of the beam web $F_{t2+3,wb,Rd}$

$b_{eff,t,wb} = \min(l_{eff,2+3,cp}; l_{eff,2+3,nc})$
$F_{t2+3,wb,Rd} = \frac{b_{eff,t,wb} t_{wb} f_{y,wb}}{\gamma_{M0}}$

Design compression resistance of a beam flange and the beam web $F_{c,fb,Rd}$

$M_{c,Rd} = W_{el,yb} f_{yb} / \gamma_{M0}$
$F_{c,fb,Rd} = \frac{M_{c,Rd}}{(h_b - t_{fb})}$

Resistance of second inner bolt-row $F_{t3,Rd}$:

$F_{t3,Rd} = \min \left(\begin{array}{l} F_{t3,ep,Rd} = \min(F_{T1,Rd}; F_{T2,Rd}; F_{T3,Rd}); \\ F_{t3,wb,Rd}; \\ F_{t2+3,ep,Rd} - F_{t2,Rd}; \\ F_{t2+3,wb,Rd} - F_{t2,Rd}; \\ F_{c,fb,Rd} - F_{t1,Rd} - F_{t2,Rd} \end{array} \right)$
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Design moment resistance of the joint $M_{j,Rd-}$

$d_1 = \left(\frac{(h - t_{fb})}{\cos \alpha} + p_{1.1.1.uf} \right) - t_{ep} \tan \alpha$	$d_2 = d_1 - p_{1.1.1.uf}$
$d_3 = d_2 - p_{1.2.uf}$	
$M_{j,Rd-} = \sum_{i=1}^3 F_{ti,Rd} d_i$	

5.3. Calculation of the joint for sagging bending moment $M_{j,Rd+}$

5.3.1. Outer bolt-row (1st bolt-row)

$e_x = e_{1,lf}$	$m_x = d_1 - e_x - 0.8z_1$
$d_1 = e_{1,lf} + p_{1.1.1,lf} - \frac{t_{fb}}{2 \cos \alpha}$	$z_1 = \frac{a_f}{\cos \left(\frac{90 - \alpha}{2} \right)}$
$n = \min(e_{min}; 1.25m_x)$	

Calculation of effective lengths

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular patterns $l_{eff,1,cp} = \min \left(\begin{array}{l} 2\pi m_x; \\ \pi m_x + w; \\ \pi m_x + 2e \end{array} \right)$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Non-circular patterns $l_{eff,1,nc} = \min \left(\begin{array}{l} 4m_x + 1.25e_x; \\ e + 2m_x + 0.625e_x; \\ 0.5b_{ep}; \\ 0.5w + 2m_x + 0.625e_x \end{array} \right)$
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Design tension resistance $F_{t1,ep,Rd}$

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Failure mode 1 	$l_{eff,1} = \min(l_{eff,1,cp}; l_{eff,1,nc})$ $M_{pl,1,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,1} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$ $F_{T1,Rd} = \frac{4M_{pl,1,Rd}}{m_x}$
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Failure mode 2 	$l_{eff,2} = l_{eff,1,nc}$ $M_{pl,2,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,2} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$ $F_{T2,Rd} = \frac{2M_{pl,2,Rd} + n \sum F_{t,Rd}}{m_x + n}$
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Failure mode 3 	$F_{T3,Rd} = \sum F_{t,Rd}$

Resistance of outer bolt-row $F_{t1,Rd}$:

$F_{t1,Rd} = F_{t1,ep,Rd} = \min(F_{T1,Rd}; F_{T2,Rd}; F_{T3,Rd})$
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5.3.2. First inner bolt-row (2nd bolt-row)

$e_x = e_{1,lf}$	$m_2 = e_x + d_2 - d_1 - \frac{t_{fb}}{\cos\alpha} - 0.8z_2$
$z_2 = \frac{a_f}{\cos\left(\frac{90 + \alpha}{2}\right)}$	$m = \frac{w - t_{wb} - 2 \cdot 0.8 \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot a_w}{2}$
	$n = \min(e_{min}; 1.25m)$

Calculation of effective lengths

• Circular patterns	• Non-circular patterns
$l_{eff,2,cp} = 2\pi m$	$l_{eff,2,nc} = \alpha m$

Design tension resistance $F_{t2,ep,Rd}$

• Failure mode 1	$l_{eff,1} = \min(l_{eff,2,cp}; l_{eff,2,nc})$ $M_{pl,1,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,1} t_{ep}^2 \frac{f_y}{\gamma_{M0}}$ $F_{T1,Rd} = \frac{4M_{pl,1,Rd}}{m}$
• Failure mode 2	$l_{eff,2} = l_{eff,2,nc}$ $M_{pl,2,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,2} t_{ep}^2 \frac{f_y}{\gamma_{M0}}$ $F_{T2,Rd} = \frac{2M_{pl,2,Rd} + n \sum F_{t,Rd}}{m + n}$
• Failure mode 3	$F_{T3,Rd} = \sum F_{t,Rd}$
$F_{t2,ep,Rd} = \min(F_{T1,Rd}; F_{T2,Rd}; F_{T3,Rd})$	

Design tension resistance of the beam web $F_{t2,wb,Rd}$

$b_{eff,t,wb} = \min(l_{eff,2,cp}; l_{eff,2,nc})$
$F_{t2,wb,Rd} = \frac{b_{eff,t,wb} t_{wb} f_{y,wb}}{\gamma_{M0}}$

Design compression resistance of a beam flange and the beam web $F_{c,fb,Rd}$

$M_{c,Rd} = W_{el,yb} \frac{f_{yb}}{\gamma_{M0}}$
$F_{c,fb,Rd} = \frac{M_{c,Rd}}{(h_b - t_{fb})}$

Resistance of first inner bolt-row $F_{t2,Rd}$

$F_{t2,Rd} = \min\left(\begin{matrix} F_{t2,ep,Rd} = \min(F_{T1,Rd}; F_{T2,Rd}; F_{T3,Rd}); \\ F_{t2,wb,Rd}; \\ F_{c,fb,Rd} - F_{t1,Rd} \end{matrix}\right)$
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5.3.3. Second inner bolt-row (erection bolt-row or 3rd bolt-row)

Calculation of effective lengths

• Circular patterns	• Non-circular patterns
$l_{eff,3,cp} = 2\pi m$	$l_{eff,3,nc} = 4m + 1.25e$

Design tension resistance $F_{t3,ep,Rd}$

• Failure mode 1	$l_{eff,1} = \min(l_{eff,3,cp}; l_{eff,3,nc})$ $M_{pl,1,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,1} t_{ep}^2 \frac{f_y}{\gamma_{M0}}$
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	$F_{T1,Rd} = \frac{4M_{pl,1,Rd}}{m}$
• Failure mode 2	$l_{eff,2} = l_{eff,3,nc}$ $M_{pl,2,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,2} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$ $F_{T2,Rd} = \frac{2M_{pl,2,Rd} + n \sum F_{t,Rd}}{m+n}$
• Failure mode 3	$F_{T3,Rd} = \sum F_{t,Rd}$
$F_{t3,ep,Rd} = \min(F_{T1,Rd}; F_{T2,Rd}; F_{T3,Rd})$	

Design tension resistance of the beam web $F_{t3,wb,Rd}$

$b_{eff,t,wb} = \min(l_{eff,3,cp}; l_{eff,3,nc})$
$F_{t3,wb,Rd} = \frac{b_{eff,t,wb} t_{wb} f_{y,wb}}{\gamma_{M0}}$

Design compression resistance of a beam flange and the beam web $F_{c,fb,Rd}$

$M_{c,Rd} = W_{el,yb} f_{yb} / \gamma_{M0}$
$F_{c,fb,Rd} = \frac{M_{c,Rd}}{(h_b - t_{fb})}$

Group of first and second inner bolt-rows (2nd and 3rd bolt-rows)

Calculation of effective lengths

• First inner bolt-row considered as part of a group	
Circular patterns	Non-circular patterns
$l_{eff,2,cp} = \pi m + p$	$l_{eff,2,nc} = 0.5p + am - (2m + 0.625e)$
• Second inner bolt-row considered as part of a group	
Circular patterns	Non-circular patterns
$l_{eff,3,cp} = \pi m + p$	$l_{eff,3,nc} = 2m + 0.625e + 0.5p$
• First and second inner bolt-row	
Circular patterns	Non-circular patterns
$l_{eff,2+3,cp} = l_{eff,2,cp} + l_{eff,3,cp}$	$l_{eff,2+3,nc} = l_{eff,2,nc} + l_{eff,3,nc}$

Design tension resistance $F_{t2+3,ep,Rd}$

• Failure mode 1	$l_{eff,1}$ $= \min(l_{eff,2+3,cp}; l_{eff,2+3,nc})$ $M_{pl,1,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,1} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$ $F_{T1,Rd} = \frac{4M_{pl,1,Rd}}{m}$
• Failure mode 2	$l_{eff,2} = l_{eff,2+3,nc}$ $M_{pl,2,Rd} = 0.25 \sum l_{eff,2} t_{ep}^2 f_y / \gamma_{M0}$ $F_{T2,Rd} = \frac{2M_{pl,2,Rd} + n \sum F_{t,Rd}}{m+n}$
• Failure mode 3	$F_{T3,Rd} = \sum F_{t,Rd}$
$F_{t2+3,ep,Rd} = \min(F_{T1,Rd}; F_{T2,Rd}; F_{T3,Rd})$	

Design tension resistance of the beam web $F_{t2+3,wb,Rd}$

$b_{eff,t,wb} = \min(l_{eff,2+3,cp}; l_{eff,2+3,nc})$
$F_{t2+3,wb,Rd} = \frac{b_{eff,t,wb} t_{wb} f_{y,wb}}{\gamma_{M0}}$

Design compression resistance of a beam flange and the beam web $F_{c,fb,Rd}$

$M_{c,Rd} = W_{el,yb} f_{yb} / \gamma_{M0}$
$F_{c,fb,Rd} = \frac{M_{c,Rd}}{(h_b - t_{fb})}$

Resistance of second inner bolt-row $F_{t3,Rd}$

$F_{t3,Rd} = \min \left(\begin{array}{l} F_{t3,ep,Rd} = \min(F_{T1,Rd}; F_{T2,Rd}; F_{T3,Rd}); \\ F_{t3,wb,Rd}; \\ F_{t2+3,ep,Rd} - F_{t2,Rd}; \\ F_{t2+3,wb,Rd} - F_{t2,Rd}; \\ F_{c,fb,Rd} - F_{t1,Rd} - F_{t2,Rd} \end{array} \right)$
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Design moment resistance of the joint $M_{j,Rd+}$

$d_1 = \left(\frac{(h - t_{fb})}{\cos \alpha} + p_{1.1.1.lf} \right) - t_{ep} \tan \alpha$	$d_2 = d_1 - p_{1.1.1.lf}$
$d_3 = d_2 - p_{1.2.lf}$	
$M_{j,Rd+} = \sum_{i=1}^3 F_{ti,Rd} d_i$	

6. CALCULATION PROCEDURE

The proposed analytical formulation can be applied through the following steps:

1. Determine the bolt tension resistance according to Eurocode 3.
2. Evaluate the outer bolt-row resistance using the T-stub formulation.
3. Evaluate the first inner bolt-row, considering:
 - T-stub resistance,
 - beam web resistance,
 - compression limitation.
4. Evaluate the second inner (intermediate) bolt-row, including:
 - individual resistance,
 - group resistance with adjacent rows.
5. Determine the effective lever arms for each bolt-row.
6. Compute the joint bending resistance as the sum of contributions of all active rows.

This procedure reflects the distributed activation of bolt-rows and allows the contribution of the intermediate row to be explicitly included.

7. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

In order to evaluate the generality of the proposed formulation, an extended set of analytical calculations was performed covering a representative range of structural configurations.

Polygonal portal frames with spans between 30 m and 40 m were analysed, considering roof slopes between 15% and 30% measured between the eaves and the apex. The corresponding kink joints were designed using IPE sections ranging from IPE 330 to IPE 500, ensuring compliance with Eurocode 3 requirements.

For all analysed cases, the bending resistance obtained using the conventional 3+3 bolt-row activation model was compared with the resistance derived from the proposed 2+2+1 formulation, in which the intermediate bolt-row is considered active.

The results show that the difference in bending resistance between both approaches remains consistently below 4% across the entire range of configurations.

This observation indicates that the proposed 2+2+1 model does not introduce significant deviations in terms of global resistance, while providing a more realistic representation of the internal force distribution within the joint.

Therefore, the formulation can be considered robust within the analysed range and suitable for practical applications in the design of inclined end-plate beam-to-beam connections.

Its applicability is therefore limited to configurations in which:

- the joint geometry induces a significant inclination between connected members,
- stress redistribution within the end-plate is relevant,
- and the connection is governed by bending.

The formulation does not account for:

- cyclic loading effects,
- bolt pretension and slip behaviour,
- or failure modes outside the scope of the component method.